

Modern Requirements for the Qualification of a University Lecturer

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ABSTRACT: This article describes the modern requirements for the qualification of a teacher of higher education, the need for a modern lecturer of university to have a deep knowledge of modern technologies and methods, the analysis of strategic tasks in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

KEYWORDS: Education, pedagogy, family, upbringing, knowledge, approach, theory, practice, experience, skill.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan is in the process of building the third Renaissance. Therefore, the requirements for the qualifications of teachers in higher educational institutions are changing. We believe that the source of modern requirements here is set out in the following documents:

- 1) The book of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "Humanity, kindness and creativity - the foundation of our national idea";
- 2) Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 No PD-6108 "On measures for the development of education and science in the new period of development of Uzbekistan".

These sources set out the requirements for modern teacher qualifications. In particular, the work of the head of our state emphasizes the presence of the following ideas in the minds of lecturers:

- 1) humanity;
- 2) kindness;
- 3) creativity.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

According to this approach, humanity means making everyone literate, good is the moral education of everyone, and creativity means making everyone happy. These tasks should be taken over by teachers. In this regard, pay attention to the following statements by the President about education and upbringing.

- labiga uchuq toshadigan "herpes on the lips" (those who are afraid of the national idea);
- *fitnachilar* "conspirators" (deprived of a sense of patriotism);
- *chaqirilmagan mehmonlar* "uninvited guests" (false information);
- *ogohlik qo'ng'irog'i* "awareness call" (education);
- *daraxtning bo'shini qurt yeydi* "worms eat the hollow of the tree" (uneducated young generation);
- *bir bolaga yetti mahalla ota-ona* "seven neighborhood parents per child" (community education)
- *sen uxlaganingda dushman uyg'oq bo'ladi* "When you sleep, the enemy is awake" (proper upbringing of young people);
- *tarbiyada tanaffus bo'lmaydi* "There is no break in education" (continuous educational process);
- *bir ziyoli - bir mahallaga ma'naviy homiy* "an intellectual - a spiritual patron of a neighborhood";
- *har bir nuroniy - besh nafar yoshga murabbiy* "each luminary - a coach for five boys".

These are a set of requirements for modern teachers. In general, the dream of our President is as follows: "We must create all conditions for the youth of our native Motherland, who gave to the world such great scholars and saints as the Bukharans, Beruni, Termezis, Matruds, Khorezmians, to grow up worthy of their great ancestors".

The above-mentioned Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD-6108 sets the following requirements for modern lecturers:

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- 1) come up with new initiatives and ideas;
- 2) intellectual and spiritual potential;
- 3) lifelong learning and experience;
- 4) having individual experience and style;

We accept these requirements as a professional profile of a higher education lecturer. Note (Figure 7):

It is necessary for a modern higher education teacher to have a deep knowledge of modern technologies and methods. Because the above-mentioned Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan sets the following strategic tasks:

- modernization of the national education system;
- strengthening cooperation and integration in the education system;
- expanding private sector participation in the education system;
- increase the professionalism and efficiency of teachers;
- further development of electronic resources and distance learning in the education system;
- introduction of highly effective international practice into the education system.

All this requires a higher education teacher to have high qualifications and skills. In addition, a higher education teacher needs to be prepared for complex conditions such as pandemics. From this point of view, it is expedient for the staff of this category to work on the basis of:

- 1) reliance on modern pedagogical technologies;
- 2) relying on the latest technological advances;
- 3) adherence to creativity and individuality.

According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 31, 2020 No 824 "On measures to improve the system related to the organization of the educational process in higher education institutions" the higher education process is gradually transferred to the credit-module system. One of the key issues in this system is the selection of teachers by students. The higher education teacher is then selected by the student for a period of one year, and this selection does not take into account the academic degree or title of the teacher. Instead, a system of selection based on the teacher's professionalism will be introduced. Therefore, a higher education teacher must be prepared for any situation and situation.

It should be noted that the following social requirements are set for a modern teacher of higher education:

- a) Scientific activity;
- b) Social and political activism;
- c) Initiative and leadership.

It should be noted that all this constitutes the competence of a higher education teacher.

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According to the Resolution, the task of introducing a credit-module system in higher education and achieving its effectiveness is assigned to teachers of higher education.

It is noteworthy that in the new era of development in Uzbekistan, the requirements for the qualification of higher education teachers are changing. This is due to the fact that the content of the education system is changing and adapting to international educational standards. Therefore, it should be noted that in many cases, confidence in foreign teachers is growing. However, this is a temporary phenomenon and we must move in the direction of national training. Because it will be difficult to have a modern higher education teacher without creating a generation of national staff.

It would be expedient to rely on the mentality of our people in the training of national higher education teachers. For example, Alisher Navoi (XV century) in his work "Nasayim ul-muhabbat" defines the mentality of our people as follows:

- childcare;
- tolerance;
- courage;
- devotion.

These features should be taken as the primary basis in the training of a modern higher education teacher. Then there will be a generation of national teachers working in higher education. Because the current process of higher education attracts attention with the following characteristics:

- the primacy of the national spirit;
- high evaluation of knowledge;
- information and data updates;
- variability of teaching technologies.

In such circumstances, a higher education teacher is required to have courageous, selfless and noble qualities. In this regard, the requirements for the profession and qualifications of higher education teachers remain changing.

It would be expedient for a modern higher education teacher to rely on the following principles:

- 1) the priority of the idea of higher education for all;
- 2) to give everyone a quality and effective higher education;
- 3) strict adherence to innovation and creativity in activities;
- 4) to bring up worthy disciples.

These principles soften the modern requirements for the qualification of a higher education teacher.

A complex aspect of the requirements for the qualification of a modern higher education teacher is that a person engaged in such activities is required to have an academic degree or title. The complexity of the issue is determined by the fact that most experienced higher education teachers do not have an academic degree or title. To solve this problem, it is necessary to optimize the system of awarding degrees or titles.

Today, it seems acceptable to rely on international educational standards in the training of higher education teachers. Therefore, it is advisable to identify specific areas of training for higher education teachers. One of the important issues for this is the training of higher education teachers in prestigious higher education institutions.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 "On measures to develop education and science in the period of new development of Uzbekistan", the national ranking of higher education institutions from 2021-2022 The process begins. This will drastically change the requirements for the qualification of a higher education teacher. Higher education teachers who do not have an academic degree or title have a negative impact on the ranking level of a self-employed educational institution. Therefore, we see the solution to these problems in the following:

- 1) Maintaining the National Rating of Experienced Higher Education Teachers Who Do Not Have Academic Degrees and Titles, Based on which to Expand the Capacity of the Higher Education Institution;
- 2) assignment of academic degrees and titles to higher education institutions, as well as simplification of the system of awarding academic degrees and titles;
- 3) to promote the activities of experienced higher education teachers at the international level;
- 4) achieving its own generation of national teachers in each higher education institution.

Observations show that the material interests of graduates of modern higher education institutions are in the forefront. Therefore, in recent years, the majority of graduates are trying to work in the manufacturing sector, and the lack of interest in becoming a higher education teacher is evident. The solution to this problem lies in the fact that each higher education institution has its own direction of teacher training.

Today, many higher education institutions in the country have foreign teachers. It should be noted that this category of teachers is limited to teaching in their profession. The educational process, which is the second functional task of a higher

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education teacher, remains secondary. Therefore, it is expedient to clearly define the educational, pedagogical and competence requirements for a higher education teacher.

Decrees, Resolutions and Orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on education set requirements for the qualification of teachers working in higher education institutions. We draw your attention to the most general aspects of these requirements.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 "On measures for the development of education and science in the new period of development of Uzbekistan" sets the following set of requirements for teachers of higher education:

- knowledge of integration processes between education systems and sciences;
- to bring up young people as highly educated, physically and spiritually healthy people;
- qualified to withstand today's sharp challenges on a global scale;
- be able to improve textbooks and manuals in accordance with modern requirements;
- constantly improve your professional skills and performance;
- popularization of IT professions among students.

CONCLUSION

These requirements are shaped by modern needs.

The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 31, 2020 "On measures to improve the system related to the organization of the educational process in higher educational institutions" establishes the following requirements for teachers of higher educational institutions:

- knowledge of the credit-module system of education, the rational use of e-learning resources
- to have individual methods of teaching on the credit-module system.

These requirements will be implemented in the process of organizing the educational process in higher educational institutions on the basis of a credit-modular system.

In the world practice of higher education, a system of requirements for a teacher of higher education has been formed.

In short, the university teacher is recommended to regularly study and master modern requirements.

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